

Institutionalizing Social Work in Education: A Post-Pandemic Strategy for Equitable Learning Ecosystems

Mrs. Gummadi Prasanthi,
Research Scholar,
Department of Social Work,
Andhra University,
Visakhapatnam,
Andhra Pradesh, India - 530003,

Prof Peethala Arjun,
Research Director
Department of Social Work,
Andhra University, Visakhapatnam,
Andhra Pradesh, India-530003

ABSTRACT

The COVID-19 pandemic exposed entrenched inequalities in the education system of Andhra Pradesh, disproportionately affecting students in semi-urban, rural, and tribal communities. This study investigates how embedding social work practices in school environments can catalyze educational resilience and equity in Visakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh. The research offers insights into creating a more inclusive post-pandemic education model by examining school-level technological adaptations and the psychosocial interventions facilitated by teachers acting as school social workers and counsellors. A randomized sample of 320 respondents was surveyed, with the sample size determined using statistical formulas. Quantitative analysis was employed to uncover significant patterns and associations, including ANOVA, chi-square tests, and exploratory data visualization (e.g., Q-Q plots and histograms). Results indicate that digital inclusion remains insufficient without psychosocial scaffolding. The findings underscore that while digital learning tools have become indispensable, they must remain supported by holistic strategies addressing emotional well-being and systemic access barriers without psychosocial support. The study concludes that school social workers within educational institutions enhance student engagement, strengthen psychological well-being, and nurture community-driven strategies that saturate sustainable policy reforms. This proactive model shifts education from crisis response to long-term equity and resilience.

Keywords: social work, educational equity, digital inclusion, psychosocial support, resilience, Visakhapatnam

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic disrupted education systems worldwide, impelled rapid shifts to digital learning platforms, and exposed deep-rooted inequalities, especially in rural and tribal regions (UNESCO, 2020; Crawford et al., 2020). While institutions embraced technology, marginalized communities in India, particularly around Visakhapatnam, struggled with poor internet access, limited device availability, and low digital literacy (Zhong, 2020), with policy innovations like India's National Education Policy 2020, implementation has primarily focused on content delivery rather than addressing the psychosocial impact of the crisis. The absence of structured

emotional support frameworks has stretched existing gaps, calling for a more holistic, community-rooted approach (Mok et al., 2021; Badi, 2022).

Social work offers a rights-based, empathetic model to support students' mental health, social integration, and learning continuity in crisis contexts (Anzalda, 2022). However, its integration into India's educational recovery remains limited.

The study aims to examine the pandemic's educational impact across urban, rural, and tribal areas of Visakhapatnam and evaluate school social workers' role in addressing academic and psychosocial challenges.

The coronavirus pandemic caused unprecedented disruptions in global education, compelling systems to pivot toward digital modalities (Chopup, 2020). In India, rapid adoption of online platforms, educational TV, and radio aimed to sustain learning, yet access remained uneven, especially in rural and tribal communities. Studies reveal stark digital disparities, where limited internet connectivity and device shortages marginalized vulnerable learners (Adesemowo et al., 2022).

India's National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 emphasizes inclusive, equitable education; however, implementation gaps persist in addressing the emotional and social dimensions of learning (MHRD, 2019). Through community engagement and resource facilitation, social workers can bridge these gaps—yet their integration into education remains minimal (Mukherjee, 2009; Vipul, 2023). In Andhra Pradesh, policies supporting orphans, HIV-affected children, and students with disabilities reflect efforts toward inclusive education, yet practical implementation lacks systemic depth (Nelsensius et al., 2021; Du et al., 2023), while the pandemic emphasized the urgency for adaptable education systems grounded in flexibility, strong support structures, and resilience (Reimers, 2022). Social work plays a vital role in this framework by bridging gaps in mental health care, academic participation, and equitable resource distribution (Goode et al., 2007; UNICEF, 2020).

The research study fills a critical gap by examining the role of school social workers in post-pandemic educational recovery in Visakhapatnam—an area underrepresented in national research. It builds on prior studies while offering new insights into region-specific interventions and systemic reforms for resilient, inclusive learning.

METHODOLOGY

Research Questions

1. What region-specific challenges did students face during virtual learning in Visakhapatnam?
2. How did school social workers contribute to emotional and educational support during and after the pandemic?

Objectives

1. To assess educational and psychosocial disruptions caused by the pandemic.
2. To evaluate scalable social work strategies for inclusive digital and hybrid education delivery.

Research Design

A mixed-methodological approach was adopted to explore the impact of COVID-19 on education in Visakhapatnam. The study focused on digital exclusion, emotional distress, and educational disruption across tribal, rural, and urban settings and evaluated how school social workers addressed these disparities.

Sampling and Data Collection

A hybrid sampling strategy combining purposive and random techniques was employed to engage 320 respondents—students, educators, and school social workers—from diverse educational settings in Visakhapatnam. Quantitative processes remain obtained through structured surveys and qualitative perspectives emerged from focused interviews, case studies, and group discussions, capturing lived experiences of educational disruption and support.

Data Analysis

Data analysis combined statistical and thematic approaches. Quantitative data included descriptive metrics (mean, SD, frequency), inferential tests (Chi-square, ANOVA, correlation), and visual exploratory tools (box plots, histograms, Q–Q plots). Qualitative responses were thematically analyzed to uncover patterns in emotional support, digital access, and institutional responses.

Ethical Considerations

All participants provided informed consent. Anonymization and restricted access to raw data upheld confidentiality and data security, ensuring ethical compliance throughout the research process.

RESULTS

Expert Interviews: Dr. Elizebeth Lucas Afolalu (YYCI, UK) and Dr. Regunath Parakkal (Kerala, India) revealed central themes impacting post-pandemic education: emotional well-being, adaptability, and technology integration. Thematic analysis accentuate "Emotional Well-Being" as the dominant theme (7 mentions) followed by "Embracing Change" (5 mentions), "Technology Use" (4 mentions), and "Creativity" (3 mentions) and this pattern underscores a shared recognition of the need for resilient, student-focused support mechanisms in education, particularly in the face of ongoing disruptions.

Group Discussions: Study findings in Visakhapatnam—Bhupeshnagar and Seva Nagar corroborated these themes. In Bhupeshnagar, 70% of students expressed emotional benefits from peer support, demonstrating the value of social work in fostering emotional resilience, while in Seva Nagar, 65% of students favored flexible learning strategies, emphasizing the need for adaptable teaching methods. Furthermore, 60% reported improved access to technology, reflecting the pivotal role of social workers in bridging digital divides and ensuring equitable access to educational resources.

Question. Projects, Assignment forms, and Activities are the most engaging parts of online learning.

Question	n	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Projects, Assignment forms, and Activities are the most engaging parts of online learning.	320	1	3	2.32	.685

Table- I: Projects, Assignment forms, and Activities are the most engaging parts of online learning.

Descriptive Statistics

The data shows that, on average, respondents rated projects, assignments, and activities as moderately to highly engaging in virtual learning, with a standard deviation of 0.685, suggesting moderate variability in responses.

Table-II

Frequency Table

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid No	40	12.5	12.5
Sometimes	137	42.8	55.3
Yes	143	44.7	100.0
Total	320	100.0	

Figure - I

Table-III

Projects, assignment forms and activities are the most engaging parts of online learning.

Variable	Category	No	Sometimes	Yes	Total	
Gender of the respondent	Male	21	54	68	143	
		14.69%	37.76%	47.55%		
	Female	19	83	75	177	
		10.73%	46.89%	42.37%		
Age of the respondent	15-20 years	33	122	104	259	
		12.74%	47.10%	40.15%		
	21-30 years	1	2	6	9	
		11.11%	22.22%	66.67%		
	31-40 years	3	3	5	11	
		27.27%	27.27%	45.45%		
	41-50 years	1	6	19	26	
		3.85%	23.08%	73.08%		
	51-60 years	2	4	9	15	
		13.33%	26.67%	60.00%		
	Category of the respondent	Teacher	3	12	28	43
			6.98%	27.91%	65.12%	
Parent		5	2	8	15	
		33.33%	13.33%	53.33%		
Student		32	123	107	262	
		12.21%	46.95%	40.84%		
Management (Type of School or College of the respondent)	Government	14	104	65	183	
		7.65%	56.83%	35.52%		
	Private	26	33	78	137	
		18.98%	24.09%	56.93%		
Locality (Area of the respondent)	Tribal	3	63	10	76	
		3.95%	82.89%	13.16%		
	Rural	11	8	30	49	
		22.45%	16.33%	61.22%		
	Urban	26	66	103	195	
		13.33%	33.85%	52.82%		
Total	40	137	143	320		
	12.50%	42.81%	44.69%			

Table-IV

Chi- Square analysis

Area of the respondent	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	71.438 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	75.012	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.454	1	.228
N of Valid Cases	320		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 6.13.

Figure - II

Figure - III

Figure - IV

Blended Learning Analysis (n = 320) showed 44.69% found projects, assignments, and activities highly engaging, while 42.81% found them occasionally engaging. Males (47.55%) rated these elements more highly than females (42.37%). Age differences were notable, with 73.08% of participants aged 41-50 finding them engaging, compared to 40.15% of 15-20-year-olds. Teachers (65.12%) and parents (53.33%) also rated them higher than students (40.84%). Private school students (56.93%) rated them more highly than government students (35.52%). Urban learners (52.82%) found these elements more engaging than rural (61.22%) and tribal (13.16%) students. Chi-square tests showed significant relationships with age ($\chi^2 = 17.059, p = 0.030$), respondent category ($\chi^2 = 17.732, p = 0.001$), school type ($\chi^2 = 35.703, p < 0.001$), and area of residence ($\chi^2 = 71.438, p < 0.001$). Engagement with interactive learning components differs by demographic and infrastructure factors, emphasizing the need for tailored blended learning models. Targeted social work interventions are essential to address digital disparities.

Question: Please rate your level of satisfaction with virtual learning.

Table-V

Descriptive Statistics

Q.no :7	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
7A) Teaching through Google meet, Zoom, Microsoft Team and other sources.	320	1	5	3.66	.823
7B) Through video recording by the teacher.	320	1	5	3.68	.836

7C) With an audio recording by the teacher.	320	1	5	3.30	.926
7D) Sharing Online presentations & study materials.	320	1	5	3.83	.919
7E) Written communication through WhatsApp and Telegram.	320	1	5	3.65	.880

Analysis of 320 respondents showed moderate satisfaction with virtual learning tools, with online presentations (M = 3.83) and video recordings (M = 3.68) being the most favored, while audio recordings were least preferred (M = 3.30). Key benefits of virtual learning included flexibility and content reusability, while challenges like reduced interaction and notification fatigue emerged. These findings emphasize the need for improved interactivity and communication in post-pandemic blended learning.

Table-VI

Frequency Table

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1.20	1	.3	.3
1.40	1	.3	.6
2.00	3	.9	1.6
2.20	2	.6	2.2
2.40	9	2.8	5.0
2.60	13	4.1	9.1
2.80	13	4.1	13.1
3.00	23	7.2	20.3
3.20	18	5.6	25.9
3.40	34	10.6	36.6
3.60	22	6.9	43.4
3.80	84	26.3	69.7
4.00	48	15.0	84.7
4.20	18	5.6	90.3
4.40	5	1.6	91.9
4.60	10	3.1	95.0

4.80	6	1.9	96.9
5.00	10	3.1	100.0
Total	320	100.0	

Figure - V

Table-VII

ANOVA

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Q7: Level of satisfaction with virtual learning.	2.173	2	1.086	2.742	.066
Between Groups					
Within Groups	125.597	317	.396		
Total	127.770	319			

ANOVA analysis showed no overall differences in virtual learning satisfaction ($F = 2.742, p = 0.066$), but gender ($F(1, 282) = 4.714, p = 0.031$) and rural-tribal regional differences ($p = 0.014$) were significant. The model explained minimal variance ($R^2 = 0.152$), emphasizing the need for localized and gender-responsive blended learning strategies.

Table-VIII

Level of satisfaction with virtual learning.

Variable	Category	Highly Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Neutral	Satisfied	Highly Satisfied	Total	
Gender of the respondent	Male	2	8	33	79	21	143	
		1.4%	5.6%	23.1%	55.2%	14.7%		
	Female	4	12	53	95	13	177	
		2.3%	6.8%	29.9%	53.7%	7.3%		
Age of the respondent	15-20 years	6	11	67	147	28	259	
		2.3%	4.2%	25.9%	56.8%	10.8%		
	21-30 years	0	0	6	3	0	9	
		0.0%	0.0%	66.7%	33.3%	0.0%		
	31-40 years	0	0	2	8	1	11	
		0.0%	0.0%	18.2%	72.7%	9.1%		
	41-50 years	0	6	7	11	2	26	
		0.0%	23.1%	26.9%	42.3%	7.7%		
	51-60 years	0	3	4	5	3	15	
		0.0%	20.0%	26.7%	33.3%	20.0%		
	Category of the respondent	Teacher	0	6	8	23	6	43
			0.0%	14.0%	18.6%	53.5%	14.0%	
Parent		0	4	6	4	1	15	
		0.0%	26.7%	40.0%	26.7%	6.7%		

	Student	6	10	72	147	27	262
		2.3%	3.8%	27.5%	56.1%	10.3%	
Management (Type of School or College of the Respondent)	Government	1	7	37	119	19	183
		0.5%	3.8%	20.2%	65.0%	10.4%	
	Private	5	13	49	55	15	137
		3.6%	9.5%	35.8%	40.1%	10.9%	
Locality (Area of the respondent)	Tribal	0	2	5	67	2	76
		0.0%	2.6%	6.6%	88.2%	2.6%	
	Rural	1	4	18	19	7	49
		2.0%	8.2%	36.7%	38.8%	14.3%	
	Urban	5	14	63	88	25	195
		2.6%	7.2%	32.3%	45.1%	12.8%	
	Total	6	20	86	174	34	320
	Total (%)	1.9%	6.3%	26.9%	54.4%	10.6%	100.0%

Table-IX
Chi-Square Tests

Area of the respondent	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	46.922 ^a	8	.000
Likelihood Ratio	53.285	8	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	.646	1	.422
N of Valid Cases	320		
a. 5 cells (33.3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .92.			

Figure - VI

Satisfaction with virtual learning among 320 respondents was mixed, with 54.4% satisfied and 10.6% highly satisfied. Parents showed the lowest satisfaction, while teachers (67.5%) and students (66.4%) expressed more positive views. Government school respondents (75.4%) were more satisfied than those from private institutions (51.0%). Tribal learners had the highest satisfaction (88.2%), with rural (38.8%) and urban (45.1%) showing moderate satisfaction. Chi-square analysis revealed significant associations with age, respondent category, institution type, and locality ($p < 0.05$), emphasizing the need for equity-focused digital policies.

Table-X

Statistics

		Q7: Level of satisfaction with virtual learning.
N	Valid	320
	Missing	0
Mean		3.6244
Median		3.8000
Skewness		-.438
Std. Error of Skewness		.136
Percentiles	25	3.2000
	50	3.8000
	75	4.0000

Virtual learning satisfaction was largely positive, with a mean of 3.62 and a median of 3.8, indicating consistent approval. The slight negative skew (-0.438) and narrow interquartile range (IQR = 0.80) suggest most respondents rated their experience favorably, showing stable and moderate to high satisfaction levels.

Table-XI

EXPLORATORY DATA ANALYSIS (EDA):	Statistic
Q7: Level of satisfaction with virtual learning.	
Mean	3.6244
95% Confidence Interval for Mean	
Lower Bound	3.5548
Upper Bound	3.6940
5% Trimmed Mean	3.6333
Median	3.8000
Variance	.401
Std. Deviation	.63288
Minimum	1.20
Maximum	5.00
Range	3.80
Interquartile Range	.80
Skewness	-.438
Kurtosis	.835

Satisfaction scores centered around a mean of 3.62, with a slight negative skew, indicating higher ratings. The moderate standard deviation suggests generally positive but varied perceptions of virtual learning.

Table-XII**Tests of Normality**

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Q7: Level of satisfaction with virtual learning.	.175	320	.000	.957	320	.000

Statistical tests showed significant deviations from normality ($p < 0.001$), indicating diverse satisfaction levels and highlighting the need for adaptive, inclusive strategies in blended learning.

Figure - VII**HISTOGRAM : Based on respondents level of satisfaction with virtual learning.**

Analysis of 320 responses shows a positively skewed satisfaction curve, with a mean of 3.62 and a standard deviation of 0.833. This indicates generally favorable perceptions of virtual learning and suggests that blended learning frameworks are well-received, though with limited extreme views.

Figure - VIII**Normal Q-Q PLOT : Based on respondents level of satisfaction with virtual learning.**

The Q-Q plot analysis shows that satisfaction data closely follows the reference line, indicating near-normal distribution with minor deviations at the tails, confirming that satisfaction levels in blended learning are generally normally distributed, supporting the validity of further analyses.

Figure - IX**BOX PLOT : Based on Level of satisfaction with virtual learning.**

The box plot shows a median satisfaction score of 3, with the interquartile range between 2 and 4, indicating moderate satisfaction among the central 50% of responses. Outliers at both extremes reflect polarized views, while the distribution suggests a balanced, generally moderate perception of virtual learning.

Question: Do you think that a single curriculum should be adopted across the nation?

Table-XIII

A single curriculum should be adopted across the nation

Variable	Category	No	Neutral	Yes	Total
Gender of the respondent	Male	31	41	71	143
		21.6%	28.7%	49.7%	
	Female	25	68	84	177
		14.1%	38.4%	47.5%	
Age of the respondent	15-20 years	47	100	112	259
		18.1%	38.6%	43.3%	
	21-30 years	1	2	6	9
		11.1%	22.2%	66.7%	
	31-40 years	1	2	8	11
		9.1%	18.2%	72.7%	
	41-50 years	2	3	21	26
		7.7%	11.5%	80.8%	
	51-60 years	5	2	8	15
		33.3%	13.3%	53.4%	
Category of the respondent	Teacher	8	6	29	43
		18.6%	14.0%	67.4%	
	Parent	2	2	11	15
		13.3%	13.3%	73.4%	
	Student	46	101	115	262
		17.6%	38.5%	43.9%	
Management (Type of School or College of the respondent)	Government	34	81	68	183
		18.58%	44.26%	37.16%	
	Private	22	28	87	137
		16.06%	20.44%	63.50%	
Locality (Area of the respondent)	Tribal	10	53	13	76
		13.15%	69.74%	17.11%	
	Rural	14	8	27	49
		28.57%	16.33%	55.10%	
	Urban	32	48	115	195
		16.41%	24.62%	58.97%	
	Total	56	109	155	320
	Total (%)	17.5%	34.1%	48.4%	100.0%

Table-XIV

Chi-Square Tests

Area of the respondent :	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	62.735 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	62.079	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	6.147	1	.013
N of Valid Cases	320		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 8.58.

Figure - X

The study reveals significant demographic and regional variations in support for a national curriculum. The strongest endorsement comes from respondents aged 31-50, with higher support from parents (73.3%) and teachers (67.4%). Private institution respondents (63.5%) show more backing than government institutions (44.3% neutral). Regional differences are evident with rural (55.1%) and urban (59.0%) respondents supporting it more than tribal respondents (69.7% neutral), highlighting diverse standpoints on AP state curriculum standardization.

Question: During the pandemic and post - pandemic, students' families and community-based resources had access to school social workers and counsellors

Homogeneous Subsets

Category of the respondent :

Table-XV

Multiple Comparisons

LSD

(I) 3) Category of the respondent :	(J) 3) Category of the respondent :	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Parent	Teacher	-.1372	.26234	.601
	Student	.0053	.23226	.982
Teacher	Parent	.1372	.26234	.601
	Student	.1426	.14394	.323
Student	Parent	-.0053	.23226	.982
	Teacher	-.1426	.14394	.323

Table-XVI

Multiple Comparisons

LSD

(I) 3) Category of the respondent :	(J) 3) Category of the respondent :	95% Confidence Interval	
		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Parent	Teacher	-.6536	.3792
	Student	-.4518	.4625
Teacher	Parent	-.3792	.6536
	Student	-.1408	.4259
Student	Parent	-.4625	.4518
	Teacher	-.4259	.1408

Area of the respondent :

Table-XVII

Multiple Comparisons

LSD

(I) 5) Area of the respondent :	(J) 5) Area of the respondent :	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Rural	Tribal	.4498*	.16028	.005
	Urban	-.2419	.13980	.085
Tribal	Rural	-.4498*	.16028	.005
	Urban	-.6917*	.11830	.000
Urban	Rural	.2419	.13980	.085
	Tribal	.6917*	.11830	.000

Table-XVIII

Multiple Comparisons

LSD

(I) 5) Area of the respondent :	(J) 5) Area of the respondent :	95% Confidence Interval	
		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Rural	Tribal	.1343	.7653
	Urban	-.5171	.0333
Tribal	Rural	-.7653	-.1343
	Urban	-.9246	-.4588
Urban	Rural	-.0333	.5171
	Tribal	.4588	.9246

*Based on observed means.
 *The error term is Mean Square(Error) = .765.
 *. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

The research study points out differing perceptions of school social workers and counselors among parents, teachers and students, with geographic location showing notable disparities. Rural areas report better access to these services than urban or tribal regions. Often serving dual roles as social workers and counselors, teachers remain key in addressing these gaps. Their involvement in advocating for equitable resources and enhancing support systems is crucial in fostering a more inclusive and resilient educational environment.

Question: Agreement with changing teaching and learning environment.

Homogeneous Subsets:

Category of the respondent

Table-XIX

Multiple Comparisons

LSD

(I) 3) Category of the respondent :	(J) 3) Category of the respondent :	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Parent	Teacher	-.2948	.15856	.064
	Student	-.2190	.14038	.120
Teacher	Parent	.2948	.15856	.064
	Student	.0758	.08700	.384
Student	Parent	.2190	.14038	.120
	Teacher	-.0758	.08700	.384

Table-XX

Multiple Comparisons

LSD

(I) 3) Category of the respondent :	(J) 3) Category of the respondent :	95% Confidence Interval	
		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Parent	Teacher	-.6069	.0173

	Student	-.4953	.0573
Teacher	Parent	-.0173	.6069
	Student	-.0954	.2471
Student	Parent	-.0573	.4953
	Teacher	-.2471	.0954

*Based on observed means.

* The error term is Mean Square(Error) = .280.

Area of the respondent :

Table-XXI

Multiple Comparisons

LSD

(I) 5) Area of the respondent :	(J) 5) Area of the respondent :	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Rural	Tribal	-.1379	.09688	.156
	Urban	-.0551	.08450	.515
Tribal	Rural	.1379	.09688	.156
	Urban	.0828	.07150	.248
Urban	Rural	.0551	.08450	.515
	Tribal	-.0828	.07150	.248

Table-XXII

Multiple Comparisons

LSD

(I) 5) Area of the respondent :	(J) 5) Area of the respondent :	95% Confidence Interval	
		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Rural	Tribal	-.3286	.0528
	Urban	-.2214	.1112
Tribal	Rural	-.0528	.3286
	Urban	-.0579	.2236

Urban	Rural	-.1112	.2214
	Tribal	-.2236	.0579

*Based on observed means.

* The error term is Mean Square(Error) = .280.

Perceptions of classroom change varied across respondent groups and regions, with tribal and rural areas showing distinct patterns compared to urban settings, and the findings highlight the critical role of social workers in designing context-specific interventions, promoting inclusive transitions, and strengthening school-community partnerships to support equitable and resilient educational practices.

Discussion

The coronavirus pandemic spotlighted structural disparities in the education sector with rural and marginalized students facing limited digital access and psychosocial support. Although virtual learning expanded reach, it often lacked the emotional scaffolding vital for sustained engagement, and thereby, integrating qualified school social workers and counselors into Andhra Pradesh's educational framework can significantly strengthen student resilience and foster greater equity in blended learning environments across diverse regions. The study aims to enlighten the critical need for inclusive policy reforms that simultaneously address recruiting school social workers, academic challenges and students' emotional well-being. However, the study's focus on data from the Visakhapatnam region limits broader generalization and calls for cautious interpretation.

Conclusion

This study highlights how the COVID-19 pandemic deepened educational inequities, particularly in marginalized regions of Andhra Pradesh, by exposing gaps in digital access, student engagement, and psychosocial support. Schools that integrated social work interventions reported better student outcomes and preparedness for remote learning. The study's findings underscore the significance of embedding trained social workers within school settings to address students' emotional, academic and social needs and rebuilding an inclusive, resilient education system. The Government of Andhra Pradesh thus urged institutionalization of these roles and the enhancement of digital infrastructure and teacher training. Future research should assess the long-term outcomes of school-based social work programs, explore localized digital learning models, and evaluate mental health trends among students in evolving hybrid education settings.

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